

**A PERVASIVE APPLICATION FOR PATIENT MONITORING
 IN WIRELESS SENSOR NETWORKS**

K. Muthumayil* & M. Buvana**

* Associate Professor, Department of Information Technology, PSNA College of Engineering & Technology, Dindigul, Tamilnadu

** Assistant Professor, Department Computer Science and Engineering, PSNA College of Engineering & Technology, Dindigul, Tamilnadu

Cite This Article: K. Muthumayil & M. Buvana, “A Pervasive Application for Patient Monitoring in Wireless Sensor Networks”, International Journal of Advanced Trends in Engineering and Technology, Page Number 22-24, Volume 1, Issue 2, 2016.

Abstract:

A Multi path Low Overhead Ad-Hoc Routing Protocol is proposed for wireless sensor system. The protocol performs course revelation when required in an on-interest way. An optimal path is obtained using PSO – [Particle Swarm Optimization]. The execution of the proposed protocol is measured as far as system throughput, parcel conveyance proportion, normal end-to- end postpone and control overhead. The results are contrasted with those acquired utilizing comparable on-interest directing protocols.

1. Introduction:

According to various applications and high data transfer rate deployment in wireless communication it is necessary to design and develop a routing protocol, which can challenge the issues such as high bit error rates, fading, limited distance based bandwidth, interference by multi path and the appropriate features of the physical layer and MAC layer and so on. Also issues like energy, congestion control should be challenged in all the layers. In this paper, it is aimed to design an appropriate routing protocol for wireless sensor wireless sensor networks can solve the issues such as Energy Efficiency, Shortest path routing and Congestion control. The main challenge in designing and developing a routing protocol for ad-hoc network can adapt the various conditions of the network. The condition may change in terms of time and packet size and propagation delay. The bandwidth available between the nodes is varying from 10 Mbps to 10 Kbps or even less. The routing protocols should function efficiently according to the available bandwidth in the network.

2. Proposed System:

In this paper, a health data gathering and aggregation is carried out from multiple Intensive Care Unit rooms into a base station. From the received data at base station, it is investigated by a medical expert in order to investigate the patient’s health information. A health data gathering and aggregation is carried out from multiple Intensive Care Unit rooms and coronary care intensive unit to physician bay and base station. From the received data at base station, it is investigated by a medical expert in order to investigate the patient’s health information. It is assumed that there N number of beds in each ICU. Each bed is associated with different human body sensors like ECG-sensor, EMG-sensor and pressure regulator sensor, heart beat accelerometer and so on. The system model is shown in figure 1.

Figure 1: System Model

2.1 Route Tracing:

Node S transmits a data to Node D, through several intermediate nodes by choosing a best shortest path in the network G. The number of intermediate nodes depends on the distance between the node S and Node D. During the data transmission, the intermediate node information is saved in a routing table and it is shown in Table.1.

REC-ID	NODE-ID	REC-TM	SND-TM	DES-ID
N13	N16	10:39	10:42	N23

Table 1: Routing Table

2.2 Route Maintenance:

The source node and the destination node are dynamic and located anywhere in the network. Since, the source node and the destination node are dynamic, the routing path between the nodes is also dynamic and changeable and the number of paths between the source and destination node is more. Therefore, a best optimal path is selected after discover various paths. And, it is necessary to maintain the information about the route for a complete round of one success transmission. The various discovered routes and the route information are maintained in a routing table for various further activities.

3. Optimal Path Selection Using PSO:

Particle swarm optimization is one of the stochastic optimization approach, used for the social behavior of bird flocks. It is a population based searching approach where each individual is considered as particles. The particles are grouped into a swarm which was developed by Kennedy and Eberhart and these particles represent a candidate solution to the optimization problem. All the particles are flown in a multi-dimensional space and they adjust their positions in the searching space due to experience with the neighbor particles. Each particle can sit in a better position by themselves according to the neighbor particle's position towards an optimal solution. This position adjustment repeatedly done in order to fetch the best position can bring an optimal solution during they fly on the search space. The best optimal value is obtained by comparing the current value with the predefined fitness value. PSO is very simple and advanced than GA, it is selected for finding the optimal path in this paper. It is essential to determine all the possible alternative routes among each source and destination pair of nodes. The paths are generated on a grid network. In this paper, PSO is used for path discovery and the generated paths information is stored in a table for future verification.

4. Simulation Results:

The simulation results are obtained from Network Simulator-2 for a number of rounds is analyzed and the values are plotted in the form graph. The conclusions are drawn from the graph. Figure 2 and Figure 3 plot throughput, average end-to-end delay against network size respectively.

Figure 2: Network Size vs. Throughput

Figure 3: Network Size vs. Latency

5. Conclusion:

Results depict that outperforms the existing three protocols in terms of throughput, PDR and control overhead. Although the performance of the protocols is not at the same standard as that of terrestrial ad hoc networks, the results are still valid and perfectly satisfactory under the given conditions and assumptions. In order to improve the performance of, other protocol categories should be explored.

6. References:

1. F. Akyildiz, D. Pompili, and T. Melodia, "Wireless Sensor Networks: Research Challenges," Elsevier Ad Hoc Networks, 2005.

2. J. Kong, J.-H. Cui, D. Wu, and M. Gerla, "Building Wireless Ad-hoc Networks and Sensor Networks for Large Scale Real-time Aquatic Applications", IEEE- MILCOM - 2005.
3. Salvador Climent, Juan Vicente Capella, "Wireless Sensor Networks: A New Energy Efficient and Robust Architecture", Sensors-2012.
4. Capella, J.V, "Wireless Sensor Networks: A New Efficient and Robust Architecture Based on Dynamic Hierarchy of Clusters", Ph.D. Thesis-2010.
5. Rony Hasinur Rahman, Craig Benson, Frank Jiang, "LOARP: A Low Overhead Routing Protocol for Wireless Sensor Networks", Journal of Networks, Vol. 8, No. 2, February 2013.